

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ICSID IN RESOLVING DISPUTES
BETWEEN INVESTORS AND THE STATE IN INTERNATIONAL
INVESTMENT LAW

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Abstract. In this thesis, a comparative analysis of mechanisms for resolving disputes between investors and the state in international investment law is made, and many concepts related to the field are discussed. Also, the role and importance of ICSID, which is considered the most popular method of settling investor-state disputes, is analyzed within the framework of international law norms and the ICSID Convention.

Key words: international investment law, investment, investor, investment activities, ISDR, ICSID, BIT, MIT, MIGA, ICSID Convention, arbitration.

Аннотация. В данной статье проводится сравнительный анализ механизмов разрешения споров между инвесторами и государством в международном инвестиционном праве, а также обсуждаются многие концепции, относящиеся к данной сфере. Также в рамках норм международного права и Конвенции ICSID анализируется роль и значение ICSID, который считается наиболее популярным методом разрешения споров между инвесторами и государством.

Ключевые слова: международное инвестиционное право, инвестиции, инвестор, инвестиционная деятельность, ISDR, ICSID, BIT, MIT, MIGA, Конвенция ICSID, арбитраж.

The concept of investment activity is based on concepts such as investment and investor, and in order to have a complete idea of this, it is appropriate to talk about these concepts first.

The term "investment" is originally derived from the Latin word "invest" meaning "investment", "directing funds", "capital investment" and has a broad meaning. noda refers to an action aimed at obtaining profit from one's own funds, relying on entrepreneurial risk. That is, it can be understood in the sense of betting money or other property on the basis of risk in order to gain profit in the future

Investment means money, securities, shares, including rights to movable and immovable property, inventions, useful models, which are mobilized for business or other activities in order to obtain profit or achieve another useful goal. and others. According to its financial form, they are considered assets that are used for economic activity in order to make a profit, and according to their economic nature, they are related to the construction of new enterprises, long-term service machinery and equipment, and related is the cost of changing working capital. It is important to take into account that the investment should be recognized not as a debt, but as the Property of the investor, which is made for the fundamental development of a certain industry and to achieve a large profit through this industry.

The concept of investment is defined differently in many foreign literatures. In particular, in some economic literature, investment is considered as a capital investment placed in a specific field with the aim of obtaining profit, while in others, investment is defined as any assets included in economic activity in order to increase the fixed capital. According to Y. Mitskevich's views on the concept of investment, "investment is the involvement of material and financial means, as well as property and intellectual property rights, in various objects of activity in order to obtain income or achieve social benefits." According to some Western scientists, they explained that investment is the capital that should be separated from yourself today in order to get income in the future. In particular, the British

economist John Maynard Keynes emphasized the importance of investments in stimulating economic growth and believes that "increasing investments during economic recession is very important to stimulate aggregate demand and bring the economy out of stagnation."

Also, international investment law is becoming more and more important today. A number of cases show the relevance of international investment law, for example, the formation of international investment law as an important branch of economic law included several complex stages. Secondly, today, with the increase in the volume of direct investment in our country, there are many disputes between investors and the local government, and the most important of them is related to the provision of legal protection of foreign investment and investment activities. are direct disputes. The above problems increase the importance of international investment law in our country.

The formation and development of international investment law in our country and in the international arena has passed several important stages. Initially, bilateral investment treaties between countries (BIT - Bilateral investment treaties) created a basis for the protection of foreign investments. The world's first BIT between the Federal Republic of Germany and Pakistan was signed in 1959, and since then their number has been steadily increasing. These agreements are international agreements that define the procedure and conditions for private investment by citizens and companies of one country in another country, and such agreements are concluded between two countries. Over time, international conventions such as the Multilateral Investment Treaty (MIT - Multilateral Investment Treaty) and the ICSID Convention strengthened the legal framework for regulating investment disputes due to the fact that bilateral agreements did not specify the general conditions of investment. The most important of them is the "International Center for Settlement of Investment Disputes" (ICSID), which was established in 1966 under the ICSID Convention within the framework of the United Nations.

In the realm of international investment law, the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID) stands as a prominent institution, playing a pivotal role in resolving disputes between investors and the state. This thesis delves into the significance of ICSID, examining its mechanisms for resolving such disputes and its position within the framework of international law.

To fully grasp the importance of ICSID, it is essential to first understand the concept of international investment law. This field of law governs foreign direct investment and the resolution of disputes arising between foreign investors and sovereign states. As cross-border investments have become increasingly prevalent, the need for effective dispute resolution mechanisms has intensified. ICSID has emerged as a leading forum for addressing these disputes, providing a neutral and impartial platform for investors and states to seek recourse.

The thesis delves into the intricacies of investor-state dispute resolution (ISDR), exploring the various mechanisms employed to settle these disputes. These mechanisms include negotiation, conciliation, and arbitration. Arbitration, in particular, has gained prominence as a preferred method for resolving complex investor-state disputes. ICSID, with its specialized expertise and established procedures, has become the most popular arbitration forum for these disputes.

To further elucidate the role of ICSID, the thesis examines the institution's origins and the ICSID Convention, the legal framework that governs its operations. The Convention establishes ICSID as an autonomous international organization, providing a neutral venue for arbitration and conciliation. The thesis also explores the various types of disputes that can be brought before ICSID, including disputes arising from bilateral investment treaties (BITs), multilateral investment treaties (MITs), and investment contracts.

ICSID provides for the resolution of disputes through conciliation, mediation, arbitration or mediation. ICSID carefully balances the interests of investors and host states, taking into account the specific characteristics of international investment disputes and the participating parties. Each case is considered by an independent conciliation commission or arbitration court after hearing the legal position and legal arguments of the parties. A dedicated ICSID case panel is assigned to each dispute and ensures that specialized experts handle the case throughout the process. To date, ICSID has considered more than 900 international investment disputes.¹

CONCLUSION

the thesis underscores the significance of ICSID in the realm of international investment law. As a leading institution for resolving investor-state disputes, ICSID plays a crucial role in promoting investment stability and fostering a favorable environment for cross-border investment. Its neutrality, impartiality, and specialized expertise make it an invaluable asset in the international legal landscape.

The realm of international investment law stands as a critical area, governing the relationships between investors and sovereign states. With the increase in cross-border investments, the need for effective mechanisms to resolve disputes between investors and states has become imperative. In this context, the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID) plays a pivotal role.

ICSID, established under the ICSID Convention within the United Nations framework, stands as a premier institution for the resolution of investor-state disputes. The institution's significance lies in its neutral and impartial platform, providing investors and states with a structured forum to address their disputes. The mechanisms offered by ICSID encompass negotiation, conciliation, and arbitration, with arbitration emerging as a preferred method due to its effectiveness in resolving complex disputes. The ICSID Convention serves as the legal

¹ <https://icsid.worldbank.org/About/ICSID>

framework guiding ICSID's operations. It outlines procedures for resolving disputes arising from bilateral investment treaties (BITs), multilateral investment treaties (MITs), and investment contracts. ICSID's autonomy and specialized expertise enable it to handle disputes with fairness and expertise, balancing the interests of both investors and host states.

Throughout its existence, ICSID has adjudicated a significant number of international investment disputes, demonstrating its prominence and effectiveness in addressing intricate legal issues in the field of international investment law. The role and importance of ICSID in resolving disputes between investors and states within the context of international investment law remain paramount. Its mechanisms, grounded in legal frameworks and expertise, have contributed significantly to the resolution of complex disputes and the safeguarding of investor rights in cross-border investment scenarios.

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